

DIGITAL PIRACY IN UZBEKISTAN: A DELPHI STUDY ON KEY DRIVERS AND POLICY SOLUTIONS

M. Isayeva

Seoul National University

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Abstract. *Digital piracy is a major concern for the software and digital media industries. This study aims to identify the factors driving engagement in digital piracy in Uzbekistan and to develop appropriate anti-piracy strategies. The findings are based on a survey conducted with senior government officials who are experts in ICT and intellectual property rights in Uzbekistan. A Delphi approach was employed for the analysis. This research provides valuable insights and recommendations for companies producing digital goods, as well as for regulatory authorities in Uzbekistan, to devise more effective strategies to reduce digital piracy.*

Keywords: *digital piracy, DELPHI method, intellectual property, the market of digital products and services, Uzbekistan.*

Introduction

Digital piracy is a worldwide concern, with a high rate of intellectual property violations posing a significant threat to innovation. To foster innovation, effective copyright regulation is essential. Unfortunately, many countries lack an economic and legal balance between copyright holders and consumers (Terra, 2016).

In Uzbekistan, no official statistics are available on the consumption of pirated digital content. However, many of the most popular web pages host pirated goods, including music and audio-visual files. Reports suggest that 90% of the content on over 250 multimedia websites is pirated from other sources (Хамидов, 2016). The average software piracy rate in Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan consistently fluctuates around 90% (Бурба, 2013). In Uzbekistan, it is common to buy, copy, and share pirated digital products from both national and international companies (Infocom.uz, 2005), Pirated movies are often available for viewing and downloading before their official release (Маматова, 2015).

According to the International Data Corporation, Uzbekistan's IT market is projected to grow by 83.5% over the next five years, with the largest growth expected in software products. However, the high level of software piracy poses a significant challenge, necessitating the development of effective anti-piracy strategies to protect the revenues of software companies (Опарина, 2017).

Copyright and intellectual property (IP) protection in Uzbekistan is among the weakest in the former Soviet Union (Трунцевский, 2015). Despite signing numerous international conventions on IP rights, enforcement remains inadequate in practice. Uzbekistan lacks sufficient border enforcement against counterfeit and pirated goods, and its weak IP laws undermine efforts to combat piracy (Khosla, 2016). As a result, Uzbekistan has been placed on the Priority Watch List of the US in 2017, which highlights countries with the most significant concerns regarding inadequate IP protection or enforcement.

As Uzbekistan plans to join the World Trade Organization (WTO) (Исаев, 2018), it must amend its legislation on IP rights to align with WTO agreements (Sharapov, 2015). Efforts to

combat digital piracy have included increasing cooperation with the United States (Долуханов, 2018). Reducing digital piracy in Uzbekistan could support the growth of the national movie industry (kun.uz, 2018) while also creating opportunities for bilateral trade, foreign investment, technology transfer, competitiveness, and economic cooperation (Арипов).

Currently, no academic studies specifically address the issue of digital piracy in Uzbekistan. This study seeks to fill this gap by identifying the main driving forces behind digital piracy and designing effective anti-piracy strategies for the country. The main research questions of this study are:

What are the key driving factors and reasons behind digital piracy behavior in Uzbekistan?

What strategies should be implemented to reduce the level of digital piracy in Uzbekistan?

This study uses software piracy as a proxy for digital piracy. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents the theoretical background and literature review. Section 3 describes the data and methodology. Section 4 discusses the results of the analyses. Section 5 provides an interpretation of the findings and recommendations. The final section offers conclusions and directions for future research.

Literature review

According to the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), an individual's behavioral intentions and actions in specific contexts can be predicted based on their attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control. Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between these factors. Here, intentions refer to an individual's motivation, specifically how much they are willing to try and the effort they plan to invest in performing a particular behavior. Perceived behavioral control reflects how easily an individual can perform a behavior, influenced by factors such as time, money, skills, opportunities, and resources.

Figure 1. The model of the theory of planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991)

A subjective norm represents an individual's perception of a particular behavior shaped by societal pressure and the opinions of relatives, friends, colleagues, and others in their social circle. Attitude toward behavior refers to how favorably or unfavorably an individual evaluates the behavior in question. Digital piracy is defined as "the downloading or duplication of digital content without authorization" (Cuevas, 2010). The concept has been explored across various disciplines, including information systems, law, ethics, criminology, computer science, economics, and sociology (Goode, 2012). The **Theory of Planned Behavior** was first applied to software piracy by (Chang, 1998) , who demonstrated that this theory outperformed the Theory of Reasoned Action in predicting unethical behavior. Subsequent scholars expanded the model by incorporating additional factors such as perceived risks (Liao, 2010), justice and habit (Yoon, 2011), perceived likelihood of punishment and fear of legal consequences (Moores, 2009), facilitating conditions (Borja, 2015), and pricing strategies (Wang, 2011) , etc. Analyses of these extensions reveal that

while digital piracy spans various forms—audio-video, software, e-books, and gaming piracy—the underlying reasons for piracy and anti-piracy strategies are largely similar. Anti-piracy strategies can be broadly categorized into four types: legal, educational, marketing, and technical approaches (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2. Categories of anti-piracy strategies

Legal strategies

Legal strategies target factors related to subjective norms by enforcing stronger laws, increasing punishments, and raising public awareness of IP rights. The findings of existing studies on legal strategies show mixed results. Proactive legal actions, such as those implemented in certain Asian countries, have been effective in changing consumer perceptions (Hill, 2007). However, some studies suggest that these effects are short-lived. For example (Adermon, 2014) found that the impact of Sweden’s IPRED law diminished within six months. Similarly, (Poort, 2014) noted that Dutch consumers returned to piracy shortly after enforcement actions.

Educational Strategies

Educational strategies address factors related to attitudes toward behavior by raising awareness about the negative consequences of piracy. The lack of end-user awareness about copyrights and the negative consequences of digital piracy is a major factor contributing to the willingness to engage in piracy. To address these individual-level factors, scholars propose several educational strategies. The most common recommendation is to educate end users through advertising and public awareness campaigns about the damages caused by digital piracy. While educating the public is an expensive undertaking, it is not always necessary to target everyone. Younger users are generally more likely to engage in digital piracy compared to older individuals, so educational campaigns should primarily focus on young users (Lalović, 2012).

The study (Королева, 2012) underscores the importance of developing specialized training programs for civil servants to improve the protection of IP rights. This study offers a strong example of the situation in countries of the former Soviet Union (FSU). In these countries, the patent system did not exist between 1919 and 1991 and only emerged after 1992. Consequently, governments in these regions have limited experience in protecting IP rights, and their legislation remains under development (Peng, 2017). As a result, judges, attorneys, police officers, and politicians in FSU countries have historically lacked sufficient knowledge about the importance of IP rights (Tiefenbrun, 1998). However, similar challenges may arise in other developing countries.

Marketing Strategies

Marketing strategies aim to improve perceived behavioral control by offering affordable and accessible alternatives to pirated content. A recent trend in the digital goods market is the

emergence of new business models based on Digital Rights Management (DRM) tools, which establish a strong link between payment, rights, and distribution (Belleflamme, 2014). These include subscription-based business models, voluntary payment schemes, and models that generate revenue from complementary products, services, or advertising.

Another modern trend is providing feature-limited freemium models to combat digital piracy (Nan, 2018). For instance, offering customers the ability to stream digital music for free with the option to purchase it later in digital or physical formats represents a win-win marketing strategy (Maftei, 2016). Marketing strategies typically have a rapid impact and require less investment and effort compared to other anti-piracy strategies. Consequently, facilitating convenient and affordable ways for consumers to obtain digital goods is often more effective in reducing piracy than imposing lawsuits and harsh penalties.

Technical strategies

The strategies in the last group address factors that facilitate engagement in digital piracy. The Internet provides access to an extensive range of resources for both legal and illegal digital products and services. Consequently, understanding how ICTs enable digital piracy and how they can be leveraged for anti-piracy actions has become a critical area of research, attracting significant scholarly attention.

There are two main types of technical solutions recommended by scholars. The first and simplest solution is to shut down primary sources of pirated content. However, in practice, this approach often has limited impact. Due to low switching costs for users, shutting down websites with pirated content typically leads to short-lived effects (Aguiar, 2015). Another recommendation involves increasing the difficulty of locating pirated content by improving the efficiency of search engines. For instance, in 2017, Google removed over 3 billion piracy-related links from its search results (Sanchez, 2017)

The adoption of more comprehensive Digital Rights Management (DRM) methods for combating piracy is widely supported by scholars. DRM refers to technologies that facilitate the authorized use of digital products while enabling content providers to control how their content is accessed and utilized (Belleflamme, 2014). DRM serves as both an anti-piracy strategy and a content distribution mechanism. Its implementation can increase copyright holders' profits by enabling price discrimination strategies, such as versioning, group pricing, and even individualized pricing.

Despite being introduced more than two decades ago, DRM systems have seen slow adoption. This is largely because implementing DRM often requires specific legal measures and contractual mechanisms to regulate "fair use" and address privacy concerns in copyright protection (Campidoglio et al., 2009).

To summarize, each category of anti-piracy strategies—legal, educational, marketing, and technical—has its own advantages and disadvantages. A combined approach that integrates elements from all categories is likely to be more effective than relying on a single strategy. Additionally, the effectiveness of an anti-piracy strategy can vary significantly depending on the country and its specific circumstances.

Figure 3 illustrates the process of this study, which aims to develop anti-piracy strategies for Uzbekistan. To create effective strategies, the first step involves identifying the key determinants and reasons for piracy behavior in Uzbekistan. These findings are then compared

with prior studies, and based on scholarly recommendations, strategies are proposed for companies and regulatory authorities in Uzbekistan’s digital goods market.

Figure 3. Steps of the research process

Methodology and data

Methodology: Delphi approach

Since official data was unavailable for Uzbekistan, the Delphi approach was selected as the methodological tool for this study. The Delphi approach is a highly qualitative method (Wen, 1998) and has been proven to be an effective survey technique when limited data on a topic is available (Markmann, 2013).

The Delphi approach involves a structured, anonymous, multi-round survey process in which the opinions of experts are summarized. This method overcomes the limitations of traditional group discussions, such as the halo and bandwagon effects, and produces results more quickly and accurately than individuals on average (Roper, 2017). Additionally, the Delphi method has a democratic nature, relying on a structured and step-by-step process of data collection that provides all participants with equal opportunities to contribute (Watkins, 2012).

To determine consensus in this study, the **Average Percentage of Majority Opinion (APMO)** method was employed. According to APMO, consensus is achieved when the level of agreement or disagreement among the majority exceeds 50%. The majority is calculated based on the total number of responses, including “agree,” “disagree,” and “no comment.” The APMO cut-off percentage is determined using the formula provided by (Heiko, 2012):

$$APMO \text{ cut – off percentage} = \frac{Agreements + Disagreements}{Total Opinions Expressed} \cdot 100\%$$

Data collection

Data for this study was collected using a three-round Delphi survey conducted in Russian from September to November 2018. The first step involved selecting panel members who were not only experts in ICT but also knowledgeable about IP rights. To ensure that panel members had both conceptual and practical understanding, we invited a total of 31 experts: 11 department heads from the Agency of Intellectual Property of Uzbekistan, 10 professors from Tashkent University of IT, and 10 ICT managers from the Main Office of the President of Uzbekistan.

Individual invitations were sent via email, including a cover letter that explained the purpose of the study and the research process. Of the 31 experts invited, 28 agreed to participate. However, after evaluating the participants’ experience, 3 experts were excluded.

In the first round, we sent 7 open-ended questions and received 23 valid responses. In the second and third rounds, the questions aimed at achieving consensus on statements regarding reasons and strategic responses were sent to participants who had responded to the previous rounds. We received 16 responses in the second round and 14 responses in the third round.

Consequently, the final data analyses for this paper are based on the responses of the last 16 experts. Table 5 provides detailed information about the panel members.

Analyses and results

Table 5 information about panel members

Total number of experts by job category	Academia	3
	ICT managers	10
	IP rights	3
Experience (years)	Min	9
	Max	28
	Average	13
Education level	Bachelor degree	2
	Master Degree	13
	University Degree	1
A number of experts received special education in IP rights		10

First round

The first round of the Delphi survey contained seven open-ended questions. For the first part of the questions, respondents could choose “YES” or “NO.” In the second part, they were required to explain why the factor was important or not.

The most important result here is that all “YES” or “NO” questions reached consensus in the first round. These results indicate that the majority of panelists agreed that income, education, the rule of law, Internet access (both mobile and fixed

broadband), and users’ proficiency in Russian directly impact users’ decisions to pirate. Additionally, the determinants of software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan differ from those in other developing countries.

Second round

In the second round of the Delphi survey, the same questions were presented, but this time, participants could see the average responses from the first round and adjust their answers if they chose to do so. Out of the 42 reasons collected in the first round, 37 reached consensus in the second round.

Table 6. Questions for the first round of the Delphi survey

	Questions	Number of answers			Result
		“Yes”	“No”	Consensus	
1.1	Does the income of users have an impact on software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan?	13	3	“Yes”	81% agreed
2.1	Does the education level of users have an impact on software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan?	11	5	“Yes”	68% agreed
3.1	Does the Rule of law have an impact on software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan?	11	5	“Yes”	68% agreed
4.1	Does mobile broadband Internet access have an impact on software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan?	11	5	“Yes”	68% agreed
5.1	Does Fixed Broadband Internet access have an impact on software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan?	13	3	“Yes”	81% agreed
6.1	Does the users’ proficiency in Russian have an impact on software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan?	12	4	“Yes”	75% agreed
7.1	Are the determinants of software piracy behavior different in Uzbekistan than in other developing countries?	9	7	“Yes”	56% agreed

Panelists agreed on the importance of 13 reasons, while 24 reasons were rejected due to disagreement. Five reasons did not reach consensus and were repeated in the third round.

Significant changes were observed in the responses to question 4.1. In the first round, the majority of experts stated that mobile broadband Internet access impacts software piracy behavior. However, after seeing that three experts argued offline piracy is more prevalent than online piracy in Uzbekistan, many panelists revised their answers. Consequently, three sub-questions under

question 4.2 failed to reach consensus and were included in the third round. Additionally, two other repeated questions were related to the business ecosystem of Uzbekistan.

Table 7. Results of 3rd round of Delphi survey

	Opinions	Number of answers			Results	
		Agree	Disagree	Unable to comment	Consensus	Cut-off
4.2.1	Users with Internet access have more opportunities to find a pirated version of the software comparing to the users without Internet	3	10	1	Disagree - 77%	93%
4.2.5	Software companies can customize the price by using different tools of Digital Rights Management, enhance the control over the usage of their final products	3	9	2	Disagree - 75%	86%
4.2.7	The Internet is not important as people can buy pirated software from any off-line service centers or “share” hard copies	10	3	1	Agree - 77%	93%
7.2.1	Using pirated software is the best option, since many software products are not available on the national market	10	4	-	Agree - 71%	100%
7.2.2	There is a shortage of supplier (stores and dealers selling the licensed software)	10	4	-	Agree - 71%	100%

As three of the questions were related to the importance of mobile broadband Internet, question 4.1 (“Does mobile broadband Internet access impact software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan?”) was also repeated in the final round. The consensus for this question shifted to “NO,” with 77% of respondents agreeing.

Additionally, the answers to questions 4.2.1, 4.2.5, and 4.2.7 suggest that mobile broadband access does not significantly increase opportunities for piracy, as offline digital piracy remains prevalent in Uzbekistan.

The answers to questions 7.2.1 and 7.2.2, related to the general business ecosystem in Uzbekistan, reveal that the lack of legal products, and a shortage of suppliers compels small firms, such as photo studios, construction agencies, and internet cafes, to use pirated software. These businesses are aware of the importance of licensed products and are willing to purchase them but are constrained by the unavailability of legal options.

Interpretation of results and recommendations

The results of this study indicate that the main determinants of software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan are income, education, rule of law, Internet and broadband access, and proficiency in Russian.

The significance of income can be attributed to the affordability of software prices. In general, Uzbekistan’s population has lower income levels compared to many other developing countries. This factor directly impacts consumers’ purchasing power, with the majority unable to afford licensed software products.

Education is the second key factor influencing piracy behavior. Most panelists agreed on its importance and provided two primary explanations for this relationship:

- a) Users with higher education levels better understand the risks of viruses associated with pirated software.
- b) Educated users tend to believe that licensed software is more reliable and efficient.

The third determinant, rule of law, relates to the quality of governance and has several contributing factors:

- a) Users' insufficient knowledge of IP laws.
- b) The government's limited efforts to address software piracy.
- c) A lack of knowledge about IP rights among government officials and judicial officers.
- d) Weak legislation to combat the piracy of digital products.

The next factors influencing piracy behavior are Internet and broadband access. In this study, "Internet" refers to mobile Internet, while "broadband Internet" refers to fixed broadband access. Uzbekistan has low broadband penetration. According to the ICT Development Index 2017, three-quarters of Internet users rely on mobile Internet, which is characterized by low speed and high costs (ITU, 2017). As a result, the Internet's role in facilitating piracy is minimal, with offline piracy being more prevalent.

However, increasing broadband Internet access has made "torrent" services more popular, encouraging users to engage in piracy. Despite this, blocking torrent platforms and similar services is not recommended. Such actions have proven ineffective in reducing unauthorized file sharing and often lead to the adoption of covert technologies like darknets, IP spoofing, and VPNs. Furthermore, such measures threaten Internet transparency and introduce censorship (Poort, 2014).

The final factor affecting piracy behavior is users' proficiency in Russian. Panelists explained that RuNet contains more sources for pirated software than any other domain. Additionally, users proficient in Russian can easily find pirated software on other domains, such as .uz, .kz, and others.

There are also unique determinants of software piracy in Uzbekistan related to its business environment. Doing business in Uzbekistan is significantly more challenging compared to other developing countries and FSU republics (Bank, 2018). There are few local software companies, and many large firms, such as Adobe and Microsoft, lack official dealers in the country. Some popular computer games are also banned. Consequently, pirated software becomes the only viable option for users, as many products are unavailable in the national market. Furthermore, there is a widespread belief that using pirated software produced in foreign countries is not harmful or unethical.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following strategies are recommended:

Price Optimization: Software companies should explore ways to reduce prices, such as implementing price optimization schemes and offering feature-limited products to make licensed software more affordable.

Educational Programs: Organizations regulating the software market in Uzbekistan should develop educational programs to raise awareness about the negative consequences of software piracy among less-educated users. This could include incorporating topics on digital piracy into the Informatics curriculum taught in public schools.

RuNet-Focused Strategies: Anti-piracy strategies should address the entire RuNet ecosystem. This can be achieved through enhanced cooperation with other FSU countries under the framework of the Commonwealth of Independent States.

Encourage Foreign Software Companies: The government should facilitate the entry of leading software companies into Uzbekistan by helping them establish local offices and official dealerships.

Strengthening Government Efforts: The government should intensify its efforts to combat software piracy by:

Providing specialized training for government officials and judicial officers on IP rights and software piracy.

Strengthening legislation and enforcement to address digital piracy effectively.

Addressing E-Commerce Challenges: In addition to the above, insufficient electronic banking services, currency conversion restrictions, and difficulties in online payment remain significant obstacles to developing e-commerce in Uzbekistan. However, the government has recently taken steps to address these issues. The “Program for the Development of E-commerce in Uzbekistan for 2018–2021” includes measures to improve online payment systems and Internet banking infrastructure.

Uzbekistan’s plans to join the **World Trade Organization (WTO)** (Исаев, 2018) further highlight the need to revise national IP legislation to align with WTO agreements. This preparation is part of the country’s **Action Strategy for 2017–2021**, which identifies trade and economic development as key priorities.

Conclusion

The purpose of this study is to investigate the determinants of software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan and recommend anti-piracy strategies. To achieve this goal, the study was conducted in several steps. First, existing literature on software piracy in other countries was analyzed, and the main factors and anti-piracy strategies were categorized. Next, experts were invited to evaluate the importance of these factors and provide their opinions on how these factors influence software piracy. Two rounds of a Delphi survey were conducted to collect data, which was then analyzed using the APMO method. Finally, based on the panelists' opinions, a list of anti-piracy strategies for Uzbekistan was proposed.

The findings of this study reveal that the determinants of software piracy behavior in Uzbekistan are similar to those in other FSU countries. However, the severity of the issue is greater in Uzbekistan due to weak law enforcement, insufficient public knowledge about IP rights, and the negative outcomes of digital piracy. Uzbekistan requires integrated anti-piracy campaigns that include educational, legislative, and technical approaches.

Effective anti-piracy campaigns can facilitate the development of the national digital goods market. They also signal to investors that Uzbekistan is prepared to ensure economic security and stability, as well as integrate into global organizations (Lalović, 2012).

In Uzbekistan, the case of software piracy can, in several ways, be generalized to other forms of digital piracy. First, while software piracy is prevalent among computer users, audio-video piracy is more widespread and affects a larger audience. Second, whereas most pirated software products are imported, the share of local products in audio-video piracy is significantly higher (kun.uz, 2018). Third, one of the primary reasons for audio-video piracy is the pervasive and strict censorship (Morton, 2017). Therefore, it can be concluded that the key determinants of audio-video piracy in Uzbekistan are an unhealthy business ecosystem and censorship.

Another form of digital piracy—piracy of e-books—is not yet popular in Uzbekistan.

This study provides new insights into the main determinants of software piracy behavior and effective anti-piracy strategies. However, it has some limitations. The first limitation relates to the quality of data collected through the survey. There is no guarantee that the panelists'

responses fully represent the opinions of the entire population of Uzbekistan. The views of this small group of experts may differ from those of suppliers and end users of pirated digital goods.

The second limitation concerns the channels for implementing educational anti-piracy campaigns. In Uzbekistan, 5% of TV and radio advertising airtime is allocated to free commercials addressing social issues such as energy conservation, environmental protection, and respect for elders. Should anti-piracy educational campaigns utilize these free channels, or should special courses be organized? Which approach would be more effective? These questions present an opportunity for future research.

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